

AN ANALYSIS OF THE PROPERTIES OF SOME CERAMIC-CERAMIC COMPOSITE
MATERIALS OBTAINED BY CVI-DENSIFICATION OF 2D-C-C PREFORMS

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2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials, made of a stack of carbon fabrics embedded within a pyrocarbon-ceramic hybrid matrix, are obtained according to a two step CVI technique. The ceramic is either SiC, SiC + C, TiC, B₄C or BN. The properties of the materials are studied on a mechanical, thermal and chemical point of view as a function of the infiltrated ceramic volume fraction. When loaded under compression, the materials exhibit elastic or pseudo-plastic behaviors. Relationships between Young moduli (or rupture stresses) and ceramic volume fractions are given. Damaging mechanisms responsible for the pseudo-plastic behavior are described. For weak ceramics (e.g. BN or SiC + C), failure occurs by interlayer delamination whereas for stiff ceramics (e.g. SiC, TiC or B₄C) a transition from inter-layer to intra-layer failures is observed. Thermal expansion coefficients and thermal diffusivity are measured up to about 1000° C. Increasing the infiltrated ceramic volume fraction decreases the strong anisotropy of the initial 2D-C-C preforms. The oxidation resistance is strongly depending on the nature of the ceramics and on microstructural considerations. It is excellent in air up to ~ 1500° C for SiC and up to ~ 1000° C for B₄C.

Introduction

During the last years, a new family of ceramic-ceramic composite materials, deriving formally from the carbon-carbon, has been developed simultaneously at LCS and SEP, for high temperature applications. The basic ideas were : (1) to replace partially (or even totally) the carbon from the fibers or/and the matrix by another refractory material (e.g. a carbide, nitride or oxide) having higher oxidation resistance and mechanical properties and (2) to keep a processing procedure close to one of those already known for carbon-carbon. Chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) was retained as the most promising way to form a refractory matrix within the pore network of a multidirectional fibrous preform inasmuch as a large number of ceramic materials can be obtained at rather low temperatures from a variety of gaseous precursors. This processing technique was successfully applied to carbides (SiC , B_4C , TiC pure or mixed with elemental carbon), nitrides (BN) and even oxides (Al_2O_3). Some of the corresponding ceramic-ceramic composite materials are now produced on an industrial scale (trade mark CERASEP) (1-8).

The aim of the present contribution is to give a comparative analysis of the main properties (on a mechanical, thermal and chemical point of view) of the 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials obtained by CVI-densification from a porous preform made of a stack of carbon fabrics consolidated with a small amount of pyrocarbon (2D-C-C preform). Thus, these materials are characterized by a hybrid carbon/ceramic matrix in which the nature of the ceramics and the carbon/ceramic ratio can be modified. A particular attention is given to the evolution of the properties of the materials (i.e. stiffness, strength and failure modes in compression, thermal expansion, thermal diffusivity and resistance to air oxidation) with the volume fraction of the infiltrated ceramics and the residual porosity.

Experimental Procedure

The materials were obtained according to a two-step CVI-procedure. In a first step, a stack of carbon fabrics (usually ex-PAN fibers) was consolidated with a small amount of pyrocarbon resulting from the pyrolysis of CH_4 . At this stage, the 2D-C-C material, which will be referred to as 2D-C-C preform, has a high open porosity V_{p0} (of the order of 0.30 to 0.60). It is yet strong enough to be machined into any given shape (e.g. into cylindrical or parallelepipedic samples for testing). Due to the 2D-character of the material, the samples were cut parallelly (para or p-direction) or perpendicularly (ortho or o-direction) to the carbon fabric layers.

In the second step, the porous 2D-C-C preform is progressively densified with a refractory carbide or nitride according to a CVI-technique performed in a modified LPCVD apparatus and which has been described in details elsewhere (1,2). The nature of the gaseous precursor used in each case is given in table I. The CVI-densification of a porous preform by a ceramic requires unusual deposition conditions (i.e. low temperature and low total pressure to favor in-depth deposition with respect to surface coating). As a result, it is a rather slow process (as it is the case for carbon), the full densification of a preform with an initial open porosity of 0.30-0.60 requiring CVI-durations greater than one hundred hours.

In order to study, for a given material, the evolution of its properties as a function of compacity, the tests were performed on series of samples issued from the same preform and characterized by increasing ceramic volume fractions V_I and, thus, decreasing residual porosity V_p (or increasing compacity $1-V_p$) since :

$$V_p = V_{p0} - V_I \qquad 1 - V_p = 1 - V_{p0} + V_I$$

Table I - Precursors used for the synthesis of 2D-C-C/ceramic

Ceramics	Gas precursors
SiC	$\text{CH}_3\text{SiCl}_3\text{-H}_2$
SiC + C	$\text{CH}_3\text{SiCl}_3\text{-Ar}$
TiC	$\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$
$\overline{\text{B}_4\text{C}}$	$\text{BCl}_3\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$
BN	$\text{BF}_3\text{-NH}_3$
C	CH_4

No further machining of the samples was performed after the second CVI-step regarding the hardness and brittleness of the ceramics with respect to those of the carbon of the 2D-C-C preforms.

The materials were tested mechanically (usually in compression, that requires only small samples, but some tests were also performed in flexion (3 points)), thermally and chemically according to conventional procedures.

Compression Behavior of 2D-C-C/ceramic Composite Materials

Experimental results

When loaded in compression, the stress-strain relationship of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials can be discussed on the basis of three strain domains, as illustrated in fig. 1 :

- in domain I, a progressive rigidification of the material, corresponding to a delayed elastic behavior, takes place and leads to a non linear relationship which is particularly apparent for the most porous materials,
- in domain II, the material is mainly linear elastic,
- in domain III, the material is progressively damaged due to the occu-

Fig. 1 : Typical stress-strain curves for 2D-C-C/ceramic loaded : (a) in p-compression and (b) in o-compression (initial preform)

Fig. 2 : Classification of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials

rence of matrix microcracking. This important domain is extended in o-compression but almost inexistent in p-compression. Finally, for $\epsilon > \epsilon^R$, the material collapses. It thus appears that the occurrence of non-linear stress-strain relationships is a very significant feature of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials.

As shown in fig. 2, 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials can be ranked, on the basis of increasing Young modulus and rupture strength, as follows : 2D-C-C/BN, 2D-C-C, 2D-C-C/SiC + C, 2D-C-C/TiC, 2D-C-C/SiC and 2D-C-C/B₄C. This classification roughly follows the increase in rigidity and brittleness known to occur for the corresponding bulk ceramics from BN to B₄C.

The variations of the Young modulus as a function of $1-V_p$ (achieved after increasing infiltration durations on preforms having roughly the same initial porosity V_{p0}) are shown in fig. 3a, b. As said above the highest stiffness is obtained for B₄C and the most compliant materials correspond to BN.

In p-compression and for weakly densified materials ($1-V_p < 0.80$), the $E_{//} = f(1-V_p)$ relationship appears to be parabolic. On the contrary, for $1-V_p > 0.80$, $E_{//}$ increases linearly with compacity according to a law which is very similar to the so-called mixture law. In o-direction, E_{\perp} is found to increase exponentially in the whole range of compacity and whatever the nature of the infiltrated ceramic matrix (fig. 4a).

The main features of the evolution of the rupture strength vs. compacity are very similar to those reported above for rigidity, as shown in fig. 3c, d. In p-compression and at low compacity ($1-V_p < 0.80-0.85$), the rupture strength-compacity relationship is still parabolic while it becomes linear (i.e. of rule of mixture type) for highly densified materials. In o-compression, the compression strength has to be described with two characteristics : the rupture stress $\sigma_{//}^R$ and the stress $\sigma_{//}^D$ at which the microcracking damaging mechanism begins to take place, $\sigma_{//}^D$ being far lower than $\sigma_{//}^R$ for weakly densified materials. As already suggested by J.Y. Rossignol, the variations of both σ_{\perp}^D and σ_{\perp}^R vs. compacity are exponential (fig. 4b) (5).

As shown in fig. 5, the variations vs. compacity of the strains at yield-

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 3 : Variations of the mechanical properties of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials loaded in : (a), (b) p-compression and (c), (d) o-compression, as a function of compacity $1-V_p$

Fig. 4 : Variations of : (a) E_L and (b) σ_L^R, σ_L^D vs. compacity $1-V_p$ of 2D-C-C/ceramic loaded in σ -compression, in a semi-log. scale

ding ϵ_{II}^D and at failure ϵ_{II}^R appear quite different depending on the stiffness and brittleness of the infiltrated ceramics. They are monotonous for the most compliant matrix (i.e. BN). On the contrary, they exhibit a sharp discontinuity for the brittle and stiff TiC and B_4C carbide matrix, which has been correlated to a transition in failure mode.

Increasing V_I tends to decrease the strong anisotropy of the mechanical properties of the initial 2D-C-C preform. As shown in fig. 6, this effect is more pronounced for the stiffness than for the rupture strength and depends very significantly on the nature of the infiltrated ceramics. Thus, isotropy in rupture strength is already achieved for incompletely densified materials in the case of the strong and stiff B_4C matrix while it is not reached, for almost fully densified composites, in that of the compliant BN matrix.

It thus appears that the data presented in this section support a given hierarchy, on a mechanical point of view, in 2D-C-C/ceramic which corresponds quite well to that already known for the related unreinforced ceramics. However, a higher rupture strength could be expected for the 2D-C-C/ B_4C composites on the basis of the high compression strength of B_4C .

Discussion

A detailed analysis of the compression behavior of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials has been given recently by J.Y. Rossignol, thus, only the main features corresponding to the elastic behavior and to the micro-cracking damaging and failure mode will be recalled here (5).

Elastic behavior in p-compression. When incompletely densified (i.e. for $1-V_p < 0.80$) 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials can be regarded as a structure made of numerous elementary beams which are bending when loaded in p-compression, leading to a quasi linear stress-strain relationship (domain III). The elastic strain is mainly controlled by the contraction of the fabric layer. The main role of the interlayer matrix is to prevent fabric layer buckling (fig. 7a). Under such conditions, J.Y. Rossignol has

Fig. 5 : Variations of $\epsilon^R_//$ and $\epsilon^D_//$ vs. compacity for 2D-C-C/ceramic

Fig. 6 : Evolution of the stiffness and strength anisotropy vs. compacity of 2D-C-C/ceramic

established that :

$$E_{//} \sim E_C V_C^2 + E_I V_I^2 + 2E_I V_I V_C \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts C and I refer respectively to the carbon preform and to the infiltrated ceramic. As shown in fig. 8, the experimental data, for $1-V_p < 0.80$, are well fitted with such a parabolic law ($d(1-V_p) = dV_I$ since $V_C = \text{constant}$ for materials deriving from the same preform).

Fig. 7 : Model of a 2D-C-C/ceramic based on a coupling between two phases

Fig. 8 : Verification of equation (1) (data taken from fig. 3a)

On the other hand, when highly densified (i.e. for $1-V_p > 0.80$), the composites must be regarded as a porous aggregate of two phases (i.e. carbon from the preform and infiltrated ceramic) which obeys a classical rule of mixture (fig. 3a and fig. 8, for $1-V_p > 0.80$) :

$$E_{//} = E_c V_c + E_I V_I \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the elementary beams considered above cannot be considered any longer as bending elements regarding the volume fraction and the stiffness of the interlayer material. A similar evolution vs. $1-V_p$ is also observed for $\sigma_{//}^R$ (fig. 3).

Elastic behavior in o-compression. Under o-compression loading, the rigidity of the composites appears to be mainly controlled by that $E_{2\perp}$ of the inter layer material (fig. 7b). The coupling between the fabric layers (1) and the inter layer matrix (2) can be now represented by the sum of the compliances rather than by that of the rigidities (with $E_{1\perp} \gg E_{2\perp}$) :

$$\frac{1}{E_{\perp}} = \frac{V_1}{E_{1\perp}} + \frac{V_2}{E_{2\perp}} \quad (3)$$

On the basis of this model, J.Y. Rossignol et al. have established that (5) :

$$dE_{\perp} / E_{\perp} \sim dV_I \quad (4)$$

leading to an exponential evolution of E_{\perp} vs. V_I (or $1-V_p$) which is in good agreement with the experimental data (fig. 3c, d and 4a). A similar relationship is observed for σ_{\perp}^R or σ_{\perp}^D (fig. 4b).

Failure mechanisms in o-compression. Under o-compression loading, 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials may be schematically regarded as a stacking of strong fibrous layers bound together by brittle matrix bridges (fig. 7b). These ceramic bridges are the microstructural elements which break the first (when the stress in each bridging ligament reaches the compression rupture stress of the infiltrated ceramic). As these bridges fail, only part of their volume contributes to the compression resistance, the other part remaining between the fabric layers as unloaded fragments. On the basis of this model, J.Y. Rossignol has established that (5) :

$$\sigma_{\perp} = \sigma_{\perp}^0 \exp(k-1)\epsilon \quad \text{with } \sigma^0 = \frac{s_0}{S} \sigma_I^R \quad (5)$$

where k is a constant, s_0 the initial binding bridge cross section, S the apparent composite cross section and σ_I^R , the compression rupture stress of the ceramic.

As shown in fig. 9, the experimental data corresponding to domain III are in good agreement with the exponential equation (4). Moreover, as V_I (or $1-V_p$) increases, the empty space between the binding bridges decreases, a feature tending to invalidate the model in the upper part of domain III. Thus, the exponential part of domain III becomes more and more limited as V_I (or $1-V_p$) increases. For highly densified composites, the non-exponential part of domain III is thought to be related to a progressive damaging by microcracking of the fabric layers themselves.

When finally the interlayer ceramic matrix is almost totally reduced to a powder, the fibers break resulting in composite failure.

Failure mechanisms in p-compression. Under p-compression loading, 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials fail according to interlayer delamination or intralayer failure mechanisms depending on both the degree of densification and the infiltrated ceramic stiffness.

Fig. 9 : Stress-strain curves for materials loaded in o-compression (semi-log. scale)

Fig. 10 : Stress-strain curves for 2D-C-C/BN loaded in p-compression

Fig. 11 : Stress-strain curves for 2D-C-C/TiC loaded in p-compression

Fig. 12 : Stress-strain curves for 2D-C-C/B₄C loaded in p-compression

At rather low degree of densification ($1-V_p < 0.75$), microcracking occurs early in the fabric-ceramic coating, however, the elastic energy which is released is not important enough to break the fibers and the fabric layers become progressively more compliant. The weak interlayer bonding allows the fabric layers to buckle up to a significant value of strain, then the materials fails by complete interlayer delamination. For weak CVI ceramics (e.g. BN or SiC + C), whose rigidities are close to that of pyrocarbon itself, ϵ_R^R decreases monotonously with increasing V_I (or $1-V_p$). On the contrary, for strong and stiff ceramics (e.g. TiC, SiC or B₄C), ϵ_R^R raises when V_I is increased (up to about 0.20) inasmuch as the interlayer bonding strengthening due to the infiltrated ceramic is already high enough to prevent early buckling and allows fabric layer contraction under the applied compression load (fig. 5, 10 and 12).

At higher degree of densification ($1-V_p > 0.75$), the evolution of the failure mechanism in p-compression depends on the stiffness of the infiltrated ceramic. For weak ceramics (e.g. BN or SiC + C), the materials still fail by interlayer delamination, even when almost fully densified, inasmuch as the interlayer matrix remains not enough stiff and strong to prevent fabric layer buckling. For such matrices, the CVI-densification of the preforms results in a continuous enhancement of brittle character (fig. 5 and 10). A similar increase in brittleness is observed in materials corresponding to stiff ceramics (e.g. TiC, SiC or B₄C) for $0.75 < 1-V_p < 0.85$, related to the raising thickness of the deposited ceramic which enhances the notch effect due to microcracking and the elastic stored energy available for crack propagation. However, at still higher degrees of densification (i.e. $1-V_p > 0.85$), the interlayer matrix becomes so strong that microcracks no longer find an easy way of propagation between the fabric layers thus impeding a failure mechanism according to pure interlayer delamination. Moreover, the notch effects due to microcracks become so significant that fibers offer but a poor resistance to crack propagation. As a result, failure occurs across the fabric layers, the rupture surface being macroscopically orientated at about 45° with respect to loading direction, i.e. in the plane where the shear stress is maximum (fig. 13). It is noteworthy that this failure mode transition (clearly established for SiC and TiC matrices and presumed for

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13 : The two main failure modes in 2D-C-C/ceramic composites : (a) interlayer delamination ; (b) intralayer failure

B_4C) corresponds to an increase in rupture strain and thus to a decrease in brittleness (fig. 5, 11 and 12).

Thermal Behavior of 2D-C-C/ceramic Composite Materials

Thermal Expansion

The thermal expansion of 2D-C-C/SiC and 2D-C-C/TiC, measured under an inert atmosphere in both o- and p-directions, as a function of ceramic volume fraction and temperature, is shown in fig. 14.

It appears that thermal expansion in the p-direction is much lower than that in the o-direction, whatever temperature. This feature was already a well known property of 2D-C-C composite materials (i.e. 2D-C-C preform densified with pyrocarbon) in which the thermal expansion in a direction parallel to the fabric layers, mainly controlled by the carbon fibers, is still much lower than that in a perpendicular direction where the pyrocarbon contribution is predominant.

As shown in fig. 15, which gives the variations of the thermal expansion coefficient anisotropy vs. the volume fractions of infiltrated ceramic, progressively filling the open porosity of 2D-C-C by SiC or TiC tends to lower significantly the anisotropical behavior of the starting 2D-C-C preforms. The effect appears to be more pronounced for SiC whose thermal expansion coefficient falls between those of 2D-C-C in the o- and p-directions, than for TiC whose thermal expansion coefficient is out of the $\alpha_{//} - \alpha_{\perp}$ range for 2D-C-C composites fully densified with pyrocarbon (1,5). This lowering of thermal

(a)

(b)

Fig. 14 : Thermal expansion of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials vs. temperature and ceramic volume fractions for C/SiC (a) and C/TiC (b) hybrid matrices

Fig. 15 : Thermal expansion anisotropy in 2D-C-C/ceramic composites vs. ceramic volume fraction

Fig. 16 : Microcracking in 2D-C-C/TiC composites due to thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between TiC and carbon

expansion anisotropy is one of the main advantages of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials with respect to the parent 2D-C-C.

Finally, a too important mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficients of the carbon and the ceramic can induce the formation of a microcrack network, within the ceramic matrix, during cooling the material from the infiltration temperature, as shown in fig. 16 for TiC. On the contrary, this phenomenon was not observed for SiC.

Thermal Diffusivity

The variations of the thermal diffusivity of 2D-C-C/SiC and 2D-C-C/TiC composite materials (measured in the o-direction according to the laser flash technique), as a function of temperature, are shown in fig. 17. In both cases, a decreases slowly from room temperature up to about 500° C and then remains almost constant. Similarly, that of the related 2D-C-C composites (fully densified with pyrocarbon) undergoes, but more rapidly, the same thermal evolution. If at room temperature, the gap between the thermal diffusivities a_{\perp} of 2D-C-C/SiC and 2D-C-C/TiC composites, on one hand, and that of 2D-C-C, on the other hand, is significant, at high temperatures (i.e. under conditions of use) it tends to become very narrow. Therefore, on a thermal diffusivity point of view, the high temperature behavior of 2D-C-C/SiC and 2D-C-C/TiC composite materials is close to that of the 2D-carbon-carbon.

Thermal Stability

If one excepts the case of BN, all the carbides considered here are known for their very high refractoriness and remain stable in presence of elemental carbon up to very high temperatures (i.e. above 2000° C). As a result, the high temperature applications of the related 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials, in non oxidizing conditions, are thought to be limited either by sublimation or decomposition of the matrix, or by the occurrence of

(a)

(b)

Fig. 17 : Variations of the thermal diffusivity a of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials vs. temperature and ceramic volume fraction for C/SiC (a) and C/TiC (b) matrices

an eutectic reaction between carbon and the associated carbide (e.g. at 2776°C for TiC-C).

Resistance to Air Oxidation of 2D-C-C/ceramic Composite Materials

The oxidation resistance of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials depends on three kinds of parameters : (1) the oxidation conditions (temperature, oxygen partial pressure), (2) the microstructure of the materials and (3) the intrinsic oxidation resistance of the infiltrated ceramic.

Oxidation Mechanism : Influence of the Oxidation Conditions

As shown in fig. 18, at a given temperature and oxygen partial pressure, the oxidation kinetics of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials can be analyzed on the basis of a two-step mechanism. At the beginning of the test, the oxidation reaction concerns mainly the ceramic which has been deposited on the external surface of the sample and within the pore network of the 2D-C-C preform. It leads to the formation of an oxide film (made of either SiO_2 , B_2O_3 or TiO_2) whose thickness raises with time, resulting in an overall weight increase of the sample. Later on, oxygen having diffused across this oxide film (more or less rapidly depending on the nature of the oxide), finally reaches the carbon skeleton of the material whose oxidation gives rise to an evolution of carbon oxides and thus to a weight loss. As a result, the oxidation curves usually exhibit a maximum which is sharp at high temperatures and high oxygen partial pressures. On the contrary, the slopes of the ascent and descent parts of the curves, i.e. the oxidation rates, become lower and lower as both temperature and oxygen partial pressure are decreased. Finally under the less severe oxidation conditions (e.g. at 900°C and 1 atm in air (fig. 18a) or at 1300°C in air or at $p_{\text{O}_2} = 0.02$ (fig. 18b)), the maximum is even not observed at all for the test durations considered here for TiC.

Fig. 18 : Oxidation kinetics of 2D-C-C/TiC composites : at various temperatures (a) and oxygen partial pressures (b)

Microstructural considerations

As shown in fig. 19-20 for C/BN and C/SiC hybrid matrices, the efficiency of the oxidation protection of the carbon skeleton due to the infiltrated ceramic depends on the ceramic volume fraction (i.e. on the residual porosity V_p). It is maximum when the initial open porosity of the 2D-C-C preform has been totally filled and the external sample surface coated with a continuous layer of ceramic. On the contrary, any post CVI surface machining, rendering the carbon skeleton apparent, is obviously detrimental to oxidation resistance. A similar effect is observed when the material is damaged due to a thermal expansion mismatch between the material components (e.g. loss of adhesion at the fiber-matrix interfaces or microcracking within the ceramic matrix, as shown in fig. 16 for TiC). In such a case, microstructural defects

Fig. 19 : Oxidation kinetics of 2D-C-C/BN composites for various ceramic volume fractions

Fig. 20 : Weight losses of 2D-C-C/SiC composites vs. V_{SiC} (Sepcarb 10 and 40 preforms were respectively consolidated with a resin char and a pyrocarbon)

enhance the in-depth diffusion of oxygen towards the carbon skeleton and thus significantly lower the material overall oxidation resistance. This important drawback of the 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials has been overcome, in 2D-SiC-SiC related materials, by replacing the carbon fibers themselves by SiC fibers (e.g. of Nicalon type) which are known to be more resistant to oxidation (6,8).

Intrinsic Oxidation Resistance of the Infiltrated Ceramic Matrix

Finally, the oxidation resistance of 2D-C-C/ceramic composite materials closely depends on the nature of the infiltrated ceramic. It has been found maximum for SiC (up to about 1500° C in air at least for moderate duration tests)(see fig. 20). It is still good for B_4C , BN and even TiC when temperature is not too high (i.e. up to about 900-1000° C in air) (fig. 18-19). As said above, the best results are obtained for those ceramics which exhibit a good physical compatibility with carbon (e.g. SiC or B_4C) and for materials almost fully densified and surface coated.

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